

Comparative Diagnostic Accuracy of Three Pain Rating Scales in Dentin Hypersensitivity

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate and compare the diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of three pain rating scales in assessing dentin hypersensitivity. Dentin hypersensitivity (DHS) was assessed using tactile and evaporative stimuli. The Schiff Scale (SS), Numeric Scale (NS), and Verbal Evaluation Scale (VES) were employed to measure pain intensity. The independent t test was used to compare DHS and non-DHS teeth using NS. Chi-square test compared categorical distributions for VES and SS. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis determined the diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of each scale. The Schiff Scale showed high DHS in 90% (evaporative) and 58.3% (tactile) of cases, with significant differences between DHS and non-DHS teeth ($p < 0.001$). The Verbal Evaluation Scale recorded high DHS in 46.7% (evaporative) and 25% (tactile), and the Numeric Scale showed mean scores of 4.48 (evaporative) and 3.27 (tactile), both showing significant differences ($p < 0.001$). ROC analysis revealed AUC values of 0.888 (SS), 0.873 (NS), and 0.675 (VES), indicating the highest diagnostic accuracy for the Schiff Scale. Schiff Scale demonstrated superior diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity in identifying true cases of dentin hypersensitivity. Schiff scale is a clinician observed reliable, practical tool which can be considered as standardized approach for both clinical and research applications.

Keywords: Dentin hypersensitivity, Schiff Scale, Numeric Scale, Verbal Evaluation Scale, ROC curve, diagnostic accuracy

INTRODUCTION

Dentin hypersensitivity (DHS) is a common clinical condition characterized by a short, sharp pain that arises in response to routine stimuli such as eating, drinking, or tooth brushing.¹ This pain, although acute and transient, can significantly impair a patient's quality of life.² Pain which results from the exposure of dentin, where physical, chemical, evaporative, or tactile stimuli that activate underlying nerve fibers.³ The exposure of dentin is usually associated with gingival recession, abfraction, abrasion, or erosion, and typically occurs in the absence of carious lesions or pulp pathologies.⁴

Pain perception is inherently subjective, influenced not only by the physiological activation of nerve fibers but also by psychosocial factors.⁵ In dentistry

and health sciences, accurate pain measurement is essential for both diagnosis and therapeutic decision-making.^{6,7} Assessing pain reliability is a considerable challenge because of multifactorial etiology of DH and its symptom overlap with other dental conditions.⁸ To address this, various tools such as clinician-observed scales and self-reported questionnaires have been employed.⁹ However, the lack of standardized methodology has led to inconsistent findings and a wide reported prevalence of DHS, ranging from 1.34% to 98%.¹⁰

Although many studies have explored DH intensity and treatment efficacy,¹¹ there is limited evidence regarding the diagnostic performance of different pain assessment scales, particularly their sensitivity and specificity in evaluating DHS.¹² The present study was therefore designed to compare the diagnostic

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accuracy of three pain rating scales in assessing dentin hypersensitivity, using sensitivity, specificity, and ROC curve analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Population

Patients aged 20–30 years of both genders reporting to the Department of Periodontology, SIBAR Institute of Dental Sciences, with complaints of DHS were recruited. Sample size was calculated using G*Power 3.1.9.2 with 90% power and 5% allowable error. This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013), and confidentiality, and risk–benefit assessment, was strictly followed. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included patients who reported pain during activities such as eating, drinking, or tooth brushing, and who presented with an exposed dentin surface on the affected tooth. Only cases in which no other pathology could explain the pain were considered eligible. Patients were excluded if they presented with dental caries, cracked tooth syndrome, traumatized or chipped teeth, pulpitis, periodontal abscess, periapical periodontitis, pericoronitis, bleaching-related sensitivity, bruxism, or defective restorations.

Clinical Procedure

Two types of stimuli were used to elicit dentin hypersensitivity. For the tactile stimulus, a dental explorer was moved mesio-distally across the exposed dentin surface, and patients were asked to record the intensity of pain. For the evaporative stimulus, a 60 psi (± 5 psi) air blast from a dental syringe was applied for 1 second at a distance of 10 mm from the exposed tooth surface. Each stimulus was applied once per tooth, and non-hypersensitive teeth were also assessed. A minimum interval of 1 minute was maintained between successive stimuli to avoid overlapping effects. Following each stimulus, pain perception was recorded using Numeric Scale

(NS), Verbal Evaluation Scale (VES), and Schiff Scale (SS).

Statistical Analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) was used. Demographic variables were analyzed using appropriate tests. All data were compiled and analyzed using appropriate statistical tests. The independent t-test was employed to compare the mean values of continuous variables, including age, as well as for assessing the association between hypersensitivity teeth and non-hypersensitivity teeth using numeric scale scores obtained through tactile and evaporative sensations. The Chi-square test was used to evaluate associations between categorical variables such as gender, and between hypersensitivity teeth and non-hypersensitivity teeth using verbal evaluation scale or Schiff scale scores obtained through tactile and evaporative sensations. A *p*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was carried out to determine the diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of each scale. For categorical comparison, the scales were dichotomized as follows: NS scores of 0–3 were considered low DHS and 4–10 as high DHS; VES scores of no/mild sensitivities were categorized as low DHS and moderate/severe sensitivity as high DHS; while SS scores of 0 were defined as low DHS and scores of 1–3 as high DHS.

RESULTS

Table 1 provides Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants. The study included 60 patients, comprising 32 women (53.3%) and 28 men (46.7%), with a total of 120 teeth examined (60 with hypersensitivity and 60 no hypersensitivity). The mean age of patients in the hypersensitivity was 25.6 ± 2.5 years, and in no hypersensitivity was 25.8 ± 2.5 years, with no statistically significant difference between groups ($p = 0.72$, independent t-test). Gender distribution was identical in both groups (53.3% women, 46.7% men), with no significant difference ($p = 1.0$, Chi-square test).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Parameter	Hypersensitivity (n = 60 teeth)	No hypersensitivity (n = 60 teeth)	Total (n = 120 teeth)	P-value
Patients/ Teeth(n)	60	60	60	
Gender, n (%)				1.00
Women	32 (53.3%)	32 (53.3%)	64 (53.3%)	
Men	28 (46.7%)	28 (46.7%)	56 (46.7%)	
Age 20 -30 years Mean \pm SD	25.6 \pm 2.5	25.8 \pm 2.5		0.72

P < 0.05 is considered statistically significant*

Table 2 shows the association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using numeric scale through tactile sensation. Teeth with hypersensitivity had a higher mean score (3.27 \pm 1.54) compared to non-hypersensitive teeth (1.17 \pm 0.92), and this difference was statistically significant.

Table 2: Association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using numeric scale through tactile sensation

Variable	Numerical scale		P-value
	Mean	SD	
Hypersensitivity Teeth	3.27	1.539	0.000*
No Hypersensitivity Teeth	1.17	0.924	

Independent t-test: P < 0.05 is considered statistically significant*

Table 3 shows the association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using numeric scale through evaporative sensation. Teeth with hypersensitivity demonstrated a higher mean score (4.48 \pm 1.86) compared to non-hypersensitive teeth (1.20 \pm 0.82), and this difference was statistically significant.

Table 3: Association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using numeric scale through Evaporative sensation

Variable	Numerical scale		P-value
	Mean	SD	
Hypersensitivity Teeth	4.48	1.855	0.000*
No Hypersensitivity Teeth	1.20	0.819	

Independent t-test: P < 0.05 is considered statistically significant*

Table 4 shows the association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using verbal evaluation scale through tactile sensation. Among hypersensitive teeth, 75% reported no pain to mild pain, while 25% reported moderate to severe pain. In contrast, all non-hypersensitive teeth (100%) were in the no pain to mild pain category. The difference was statistically significant.

Table 4: Association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using Verbal evaluation scale through tactile sensation

Variable	Verbal evaluation scale		P-value
	No Pain - Mild Pain	Moderate Pain – Severe pain	
Hypersensitivity Teeth	45 (75%)	15 (25%)	0.000*
No Hypersensitivity Teeth	60 (100%)	0 (0%)	

Chi-square test: P < 0.05 is considered statistically significant*

Table 5 shows the association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using Schiff scale through tactile sensation. Among hypersensitive teeth, 41.7% recorded a score of 0 and 58.3% recorded scores between 1 and 3. In contrast,

76.7% of non-hypersensitive teeth recorded a score of 0, while only 23.3% scored between 1 and 3. This difference was statistically significant.

Table 5: Association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using Schiff scale through tactile sensation

Variable	Schiff scale		P-value
	Score 0	Score 1-3	
Hypersensitivity Teeth	25 (41.7%)	35 (58.3%)	0.000*
No Hypersensitivity Teeth	46 (76.7%)	14 (23.3%)	

Chi-square test: P< 0.05 is considered statistically significant*

Table 6 shows the association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using Schiff scale through evaporative sensation. Only 10% of hypersensitive teeth recorded a score of

0, while 90% scored between 1 and 3. In contrast, 71.7% of non-hypersensitive teeth scored 0, and 28.3% scored between 1 and 3. This difference was statistically significant.

Table 6: Association between hypersensitivity teeth and no hypersensitivity teeth using Schiff scale through Evaporative sensation

Variable	Schiff scale		P-value
	Score 0	Score 1-3	
Hypersensitivity Teeth	6 (10%)	54 (90%)	0.000*
No Hypersensitivity Teeth	43 (71.7%)	17 (28.3%)	

Chi-square test : P< 0.05 is considered statistically significant*

Figure 1 demonstrated the highest diagnostic accuracy (AUC = 0.888), with superior sensitivity and specificity to Schiff scale compared to the numeric

(AUC = 0.873) and verbal evaluation scales (AUC = 0.675).

Figure 1: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curves Depicting the Diagnostic Accuracy of Pain Rating Scales in Dentin Hypersensitivity.

DISCUSSION

Dentin hypersensitivity (DHS) is defined as a short, sharp pain that arises from exposed dentin in response

to non-noxious stimuli, such as thermal, evaporative, tactile, or chemical, which cannot be attributed to any other dental pathology. Several clinical factors are implicated in the development of DHS, including

enamel attrition, erosion, abrasion, abfraction, corrosion, and gingival recession.

The hydrodynamic theory, proposed by Brännström, is the most widely accepted explanation for DHS. It suggests that external stimuli induce fluid movement within dentinal tubules, which subsequently stimulates pulpal nerve endings located at the tubule walls, leading to acute transient pain. Selecting an appropriate pain rating scale for the assessment of DHS requires consideration of diagnostic accuracy, reliability, patient preference, and clinical utility. Despite the high prevalence of DHS, universally accepted diagnostic guidelines are lacking, making comparative studies of rating scales important for clinical practice. In the present study, the Schiff Scale (SS), Verbal Evaluation Scale (VES), and Numeric Scale (NS) were applied to evaluate dentine hypersensitivity using both evaporative and tactile stimuli. The SS demonstrated the highest sensitivity, identifying high DHS in 90% of cases with the evaporative stimulus and 58.3% with the tactile stimulus. The Schiff Scale (SS) demonstrated the highest diagnostic accuracy (AUC = 0.888), with superior sensitivity and specificity compared to the numeric scale (NS, AUC = 0.873) and the verbal evaluation scale (VES, AUC = 0.675). These findings suggest that the SS is more effective in differentiating true dentin hypersensitivity cases from non-cases. The findings are consistent with previous reports where the Schiff Scale has been recognized as a reliable tool for differentiating between sensitive and non-sensitive teeth, particularly in response to air stimulus^{14, 15}.

The VES identified high DHS in 46.7% of evaporative and 25% of tactile cases, suggesting lower sensitivity than SS, yet still showing significant group differences. This aligns with earlier literature where patient-reported verbal scales, although less quantitative, were found to provide valuable subjective assessment of discomfort.^{16, 17} The NS produced mean scores of 4.48 for evaporative and 3.27 for tactile stimuli, indicating a significant distinction between DHS and non-DHS teeth. Numeric rating scales are well-established for their ability to capture gradations in pain intensity and have been recommended in clinical trial design for dentine hypersensitivity.^{18, 19} Previous studies have

highlighted the diagnostic reliability of the Schiff Scale in assessing DH. Barroso et al. (2019) reported that air blast stimulus, assessed through the SS, was a highly accurate method for diagnosing DHS and demonstrated good reproducibility.²⁰ Similarly, Rocha Moc et al. (2020) observed that among various pain rating scales, SS was a sensitive and specific tool for identifying DH, supporting its validity for clinical use.²¹ On the other hand, patient-dependent scales such as VES and NS may introduce variability due to differences in individual pain thresholds, verbal expression, and psychosocial influences.²² Although these scales remain useful for subjective pain quantification, their diagnostic accuracy is comparatively lower. Overall, the present findings demonstrate that all three scales including SS, VES, and NS are effective in distinguishing DHS from non-DHS teeth, with the SS showing superior diagnostic sensitivity, particularly with evaporative stimuli. These observations are in agreement with consensus recommendations emphasizing the importance of combining both objective clinical measures and subjective patient-reported outcomes in DHS assessment (Bekes et al., 2015). The complementary use of these scales may therefore provide a more comprehensive and clinically relevant evaluation of DHS. Therefore, the present findings reinforce that the Schiff Scale is a more objective and clinically practical tool for DHS evaluation. Its standardized clinician-observed scoring system not only improves diagnostic reliability but also ensures consistency in research protocols, making it a valuable instrument for both chair side use and clinical trials. The relatively small sample size is the limitation of the study, and the findings may not be generalized across different age groups or broader populations.

CONCLUSION

Schiff Scale, Verbal Evaluation Scale, Numeric Scale are effective for diagnosing dentin hypersensitivity. Evaporative stimulus was more accurate than tactile stimulus and should be preferred in clinical practice. Among the scales, the Schiff Scale demonstrated the highest sensitivity, specificity, and patient preference, making it the most suitable tool for DHS assessment.

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